

Spatial trees consist of a collection of nodes where each node represents a contiguous region of space and the particles within that region. The root node contains all the particles in the simulation “universe”, and represents the region defined by a bounding box that contains all particles. Child nodes are defined by recursively subdividing this region along with the contained particles. The recursion finishes when a child node contains less than a specified number of particles. Such nodes are referred to as “leaf nodes” and their contained particles are referred to as a “bucket” of particles. Tree types are defined by the strategy used to subdivide the spatial regions. For example, in 3D simulations octrees are created by subdividing each node into eight regions of equal volume. On the other hand, k-d trees are created by subdividing each node along its longest dimension into two subregions such that each of the child nodes contains half the particles of the parent. The preferred tree type depends on the particle distribution and application. For example, octrees can become significantly imbalanced in representing highly non-uniform particle distributions, but each node always has a bounding box with an aspect ratio near one. On the other hand kd-trees are guaranteed to be balanced, but nodes can have very different aspect ratios.

Tree algorithms offer computational efficiencies when the traversal of a particular node’s descendants can be replaced by an approximation based on the properties of the node. For example, in the Barnes-Hut algorithm, the gravitational forces on a distant body due to all particles within a node may be approximated by a single force calculated from the center of mass of the node. If the approximation is sufficiently accurate, the traversal can be “pruned” at that node. Since the gravitational force approximation is more accurate for near-spherical regions, an octree with its bounding boxes with aspect ratios near one, tends to be preferred for the Barnes-Hut application. In contrast, k-nearest neighbor searches prefer nodes with children that are uniform in particle count. However, these preferences do not necessarily hold for all particle distributions, and the best choice of tree type for a given application and particle distribution is often best determined by experimentation.

Steps to Partitions-Subtrees decomposition

1. Assign particles to partitions
2. Assign particles to subtrees and flush
3. Build subtrees top-down
4. Hand leaves over to Partitions

Figure 4: Demonstration of the steps to decompose a spatial domain with the Partitions-Subtrees model: explicit steps (top left), a sample partition assignment of a region of space (bottom left), a sample subtree assignment (bottom right), and a picture of the associated global tree (top right).